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Summary

In this document, we describe a tool for prediction of molecular Initiating events (MIE) which are the first step in the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) representation of toxicity induced by chemicals including nanomaterials. The tool, which was developed based on extensive research to define AOPs undertaken within the SmartNanoTox project, identifies three MIEs:

- MIE1. Disruption of lung surfactant functionality
- MIE2. Lysosomal destabilization
- MIE3. Oxidation of cell membrane

Using published data from *in vivo* and *in vitro* experimental studies of nanomaterials toxicity and different signaling and functional databases, we created the NanoCommons MIE gene set database (NanoCommons GS-MIE DB). The database captures gene signatures (GS) of MIEs by integrating knowledge from KEGG, REACTOME, GO, WikiPathways public databases and custom gene sets from published data. To date, 132 gene sets representing three different types of MIE actions have been manually collected.

In order to integrate the MIE prediction tool into the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase, we also provided a web interface, and R and Python codes for access to the database and calculation of the overrepresentation of distinct biological processes for each MIE. As an input, the tool uses a list of differentially expressed genes/proteins from high-throughput experiments and calculates a prioritized list of MIEs with identified biological processes.

Introduction

To reduce the costs of toxicity testing and facilitate reduction of animal use in toxicological experiments, the conceptual framework of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) has become widely used in the nanosafety community as a powerful approach [1–3]. AOPs provide a framework for collecting and organizing mechanistic knowledge for describing the causal linkages between a molecular initiating event (MIE; an initial interaction between a chemical or nanomaterial (NM) and the biological system) and series of intermediate key events (KEs), which culminate in an adverse outcome (AO).

In this deliverable, we describe and demonstrate a tool that has been developed within the NanoCommons infrastructure for modelling the likelihood of the MIEs occurring in the context of NM-driven toxicity. The developed tool includes a database of MIEs gene descriptors, a web interface and R/Python modules for integration into various automated pipelines, including the Jaqpot computational platform and the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase.

We used the experimental and methodological basis of the [SmartNanoTox](#) project that focuses on developing pulmonary AOPs for fibrosis, cancer, acute and chronic inflammation induced by inhaled NMs [3, 4]. The tool could fill the gap in understanding of bionano interactions, and facilitates reconstruction of a sequential chain of KEs in a particular AOP.

This deliverable report describes the tool itself, gives examples of its use, and provides various codes needed to integrate it into the NanoCommons suite of tools and services available for Transnational Access (TA).

Adverse Outcome Pathways

An important aspect of AOPs is that they cover multiple levels of biological organization (molecular, cellular, organ, organism, population) as shown schematically in Figure 1, which is a clear distinction from biological networks and also presents quite some challenge for *in vitro* assays which are limited to cellular level events generally. That said, the molecular initiating event (MIE) which is the initial interaction between a chemical or NM and the biological system that triggers subsequent key events (KEs) leading to a particular AO is at the cellular level and is accessible via *in vitro* assays or from gene expression signatures.

Figure 1: Illustration of an AOP linking molecular and cellular perturbations to impacts at the tissue, organ, organism and population levels, and the types of assays that can be used to explore the perturbations at the different levels. From OECD, 2017.

Figure 2 gives an example of a generalized AOP and its components (Panel A) and shows how AOPs can form interlinked networks based on overlapping MIEs, KEs and AOs (Panel B) that represent the complex biology underlying disease processes [5]. The AOP framework defines this entire conceptual approach that assembles and organizes mechanistic knowledge to communicate causal linkages between biological perturbations and adverse health outcomes meaningful to chemical risk assessment and regulatory decision making [1].

Figure 2. (A) Generalized AOP showing the relationship between MIE, KEs and AOs and the KERs that connect them. Bioassays targeting the MIE and KEs in an AOP developed as part of an IATA. (B) AOPs can form interlinked networks based on overlapping MIEs, KEs and AOs that better capture the complex biology of disease processes [5].

While significant progress has been made in AOP development, application and use over the last decade, there is still a significant distance to go to reduce our current reliance on animal testing. AOPs and other *in silico* tools may, in the future, enable reduction of and eventually complete replacement of animal testing with non-animal approaches for risk assessment and regulatory decision making [6]. Development and widespread use of predictive tools to support identification of MIEs induced by NMs, and the resulting KEs and AOs are an important step towards achieving widespread acceptance of AOPs and accelerating the transition to reliance on alternative testing and assessment strategies and frameworks.

State of the art in understanding and defining MIEs

A consensus definition on an MIE was proposed by Allen et al., in 2014 as “the initial interaction between a molecule and a biomolecule or biosystem that can be causally linked to an outcome via a pathway” [7]. Receptor binding for example, is one type of MIE, and a lot of work has been done to group chemicals toxicologically on the basis of receptor binding. If a receptor has a single mechanism of binding, and hence is associated with a single MIE, it can be confidently predicted that a quantitative structure-activity model (QSAR) based on this training set will be highly successful. However, if the receptor is associated with several MIEs, the (Q)SAR will not be effective [7].

To understand an MIE completely, a lot of information is required: information about chemicals that

are associated with the MIE, structural features or properties of the chemical that causes its association, the types of interactions that occur between the chemical and biomolecule or biosystem, and the nature or structure of the entity with which the molecule interacts. Obtaining all this information is very difficult, and partial information from different sources must be brought together when evaluating MIEs. Incompleteness in parts is to be expected, as even the most well studied chemicals lack detailed reports of molecular interactions [7].

The situation is even trickier for NMs where less is known and both physical and chemical interactions are likely and thus MIEs may be physical rather than molecular in nature (e.g., frustrated phagocytosis); research and AOP development will need to account for these particle-specific mechanisms [6]. Risk assessment requires information on the exposure conditions (e.g., route, dose, duration and frequency) needed to cause an AO. Quantitative AOPs (qAOPs), which use quantitative data to predict risk of an AO under specific exposure conditions, are proposed as a solution to address these needs, but few examples currently exist.

Identifying the pathways related to an MIE is a major challenge, and distinguishing between an MIE and an intermediate KE can be difficult. Indeed, characterization of the MIE at the molecular level relies on *in silico* (i.e., computational) or *in vitro* (i.e., cell culture) data, while KEs at the organelle and cellular levels are typically supported by *in vitro* or, to a lesser extent, *in vivo* (i.e., animal experimentation and clinical information) testing outcomes, while KEs at the tissue, organ, and organism levels routinely depend on *in vivo* experimentation results [8]. Because of their scope, omics-based data can be used to feed virtually all information blocks in AOPs, but without time-resolved data establishing the MIE is challenging. For instance, *in vivo* transcriptomics experiments may typically include data at days 1, 3, 28 and 90. At the day 1 time point the transcriptomics data contains a mixture of different signals from MIEs and KEs, along with some responses being transient such as those associated with repair activities etc [9]. Without detailed data for the first hours of cell responses to a NM it is difficult to isolate the MIE from the differentially expressed gene sets. For example, oxidation of cell membrane can be induced indirectly, for instance, by frustrated phagocytosis, and it is not possible to differentiate direct interaction and indirect interactions at this stage based on the available data. But if we have data for the initial response period (1-3 hours after NM exposition), it is most likely to predict actual MIEs or at the very least represent the response to the MIE.

MIEs for NMs-induced impacts on lungs

In this document, we focus on three key types of MIE related to an inhalation exposure route: disruption of lung surfactant functionality, lysosomal destabilization, and oxidation of cell membrane as established by the SmartNanoTox project. More MIEs will be added continuously in the future.

Disruption of lung surfactant functionality

The alveolar lining fluid and the thin layer of lung surfactant are the first protection barrier against inhaled NMs. Lung surfactant is a surface-active lipoprotein complex in the alveolar space and its main function is reducing the surface tension at the air/liquid interface in the lung. Also, this complex regulates inflammatory responses. The disruption of the lung surfactant may lead to negative health outcomes, such as lung fibrosis [10], chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [11], pneumonia, asthma,

acute respiratory distress syndrome or acute lung injury. This MIE is the initial event of [AOP 302](#): Lung surfactant function disruption leading to acute inhalation toxicity.

Lysosomal destabilization

The next level of bionano interactions is NM bio-adhesion to and uptake into cells. After endocytosis of NM by different types of cells (macrophages, epithelial, etc.) and following different exposure routes (inhalation, ingestion, intravenous, dermal), eventually NMs are retained inside lysosomes. This cell compartment consists of a variety of hydrolytic enzymes (phosphatases, proteases, nucleases, etc) and a highly acidic environment providing degradation of foreign substances. Biopersistent NMs can cause lysosomal dysfunction, for instance, lysosomal membrane permeability that can induce leakage of the protease cathepsins and other associated lysosomal hydrolases into the cytoplasm. It can trigger a variety of toxicological consequences including oxidative stress, cytosolic acidification and induce cell death pathways including necrosis, apoptosis and autophagy [12]. This MIE is the initial event of [AOP 257](#): Receptor mediated endocytosis and lysosomal overload leading to kidney toxicity; and [AOP 144](#): Endocytic lysosomal uptake leading to liver fibrosis.

Oxidation of cell membrane

NMs can induce oxidative damage of cell membranes through lipid peroxidation, in which free radicals steal electrons from the lipid components of the cell membranes [13]. This effect might be induced by metal oxide NMs [14]. This MIE is the initial event of [AOP 260](#): CYP2E1 activation and formation of protein adducts leading to neurodegeneration.

Description

MIE gene set database

Classic enrichment analysis generates a common picture for all pathways altered by a specific perturbant. Thus, to be more focussed, we generated herein a database that focuses only on MIEs., using gene sets collected from different sources, resulting in an aggregated database. Also, we linked known pathways/GO terms with MIE, which is not trivial. This will also allow users to further annotate the gene sets according to their importance as biomarkers for the specific AO, and will facilitate use of the AOPs in Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs) since they link mechanisms and biomarkers, which can be assessed with existing or new *in vitro* assays including omics or specific assays like reporter cell lines.

For each MIE, we created specific MIE gene sets using information from the KEGG, REACTOME, GO, HP and WikiPathways public databases as well as published data and made them available at the NanoCommons MIE gene set database (MIE-GS DB). To date, we collected 132 gene sets representing the three different MIEs, as shown in Table 1. The current version of the NanoCommons MIE-GS database includes MIEs for mice as target organism, rather than humans.

Table 1. Description of the database

MIE	Description
Disruption of lung surfactant functionality	Number of gene sets: 3 Examples of the gene sets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GO:0043129 Surfactant homeostasis • REAC:R-MMU-5683826 Surfactant metabolism • SBI:S001 Surfactant homeostasis custom gene set
Lysosomal destabilization	Number of gene sets: 54 Examples of the gene sets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GO:0097212 Lysosomal membrane organization • REAC:R-MMU-432720 Lysosome Vesicle Biogenesis • HP:0004356 Abnormality of lysosomal metabolism • KEGG:04142 Lysosome
Oxidation of cell membrane	Number of gene sets: 75 Examples of the gene sets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GO:0006979 Response to oxidative stress • GO:0071451 Cellular response to superoxide • REAC:R-MMU-1222556 ROS and RNS production in phagocytes • WP:WP1496 Oxidative Damage

The database was constructed based on the Gene Matrix Transposed (GMT) file format. The GMT file format is a tab delimited file format that describes gene sets. In the GMT format, each row represents a gene set. Each gene set is described by a name, a description, and the genes in the gene set (see Figure 3).

GO:0001845	phagolysosome assembly	Tmem175	Syt7	Rab14	P2rx7	Coro1a	Myo7a	Rab20	Spg11	Rab7b	Rab39	Rab7	Srpx																				
GO:0006622	protein targeting to lysosome	M6pr	Hspa8	Lamp2	Ap4m1	Ap3b1	Zfyve16	Lhcgr	Lars	Hgs	Snx16	Scarb2	Vps4a	Nedd4	Gnptab	Gcc2	Sorl1	Ncoa4															
GO:0007040	lysosome organization	Snapin	Naglu	Acp2	Tmem175	Abca1	Hspa8	Lyst	Clvs2	Hexb	Cln5	Laptm4b	Tfeb	Atp6v0c	Syt7	5430427019Rik	Hexa	Gaa	Mfsd8	Cln8	Rab14	Gba	Chmp5	Hook1	Ppt1								
		Tmem165	Vps33a	P2rx7	Tmem106b	Coro1a	Cln3	Myo7a	Lamtor1	Tpp1	Rab20	Aktip	Vps35	Mt3	Mbtps1	Cln6	Spg11	Vps18	Grn	Becn1	Gnptab	Lrrk2	Hook3	Clvs1	Ccdc115	Hps4	Fam160a2	Arf1	Tpcn2				
		Trex1	Tmem199	Hook2	Rab7b	Rab39	Rab7	Srpx	Mfsd8	GO:0007041	lysosomal transport	Snapin	Psap	M6pr	Vps4b	Tsg101	Rbsn	Hspa8	Lamp2	Vps53	Cacng2	Ap4m1	Ubxn6	Lyst	Vps54	Ap3d1	Cacng4	Ankfy1	Stx8				
		Vipas39	Kif13a	Ap3b1	Zfyve16	Mgrn1	Rab12	Prkn	Igf2r	Ehd3	Lhcgr	Vps52	Bin1	Npc1	Lars	Vps51	Hgs	Als2	Trak2	Vps39	Vps16	Snx16	Snx27	C9orf72	Chmp5	Vcp	Hook1	Pink1	Scarb2	Vps33a	Tmem106b	Cdx2	Ccdc91

Mtm1	Lamp1	Aktip	Vps35	Ap1g1	Mvb12a	Vps4a	Vps11	Nedd4	Trak1
Vps18	Grn	Gnptab	Dennd3	Hook3	Hgsnat	Atg14	Gcc2	Rilp	Epg5
Gprasp1		Pcsk9	Fam160a2	Arf1	Sorl1	Dtx3l	Vamp7	Hook2	Rab7b
Chmp3	Rhob	Ncoa4	Gak	Cacng3	Clec16a	Sort1	Scyl2	Tgfbrap1	Sptbn5
Rab7	Hspa1a	Gm38100		Pcdhga3		Epg5			
GO:0007042	lysosomal lumen acidification			Snapin	Cln5	Atp6v0c		Ppt1	Cln3
Cln6	Grn	Ccdc115		Tmem199					
GO:0016237	lysosomal microautophagy			Rb1cc1	Atg13	Atg7			
GO:0016256	N-glycan processing to lysosome				Gnptab				
GO:0033299	secretion of lysosomal enzymes			Nr1h3	Bloc1s6	M6pr	Nagpa	Gnptab	Bloc1s3
	Nr1h2								
GO:0035751	regulation of lysosomal lumen pH			Snapin	Tmem175		Cln5	Atp6v0c	
5430427	O19Rik	Ppt1	Tmem165	Vps33a	Cln3	Cln6	Grn	Lrrk2	Ccdc115
	Tmem199								

Figure 3. The structure of the GMT file format.

The resulting database was used as a basis for further statistical analysis. We used R and Python client libraries for g:Profiler tool [15] to perform an overrepresentation analysis for MIE terms using the cumulative hypergeometric test.

Access to the MIE prediction tool

The MIE prediction tool software implementation enables the nanotoxicology community to easily access the results using either the developed web interface (for non-programming users) or by integrating the MIE prediction tool into various automated pipelines, including the Jaqpot computational platform and the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase. To facilitate these different modes of access, a user friendly web interface was designed, as well as provision of scripts to facilitate access the R and Python language versions of the tool. In both cases, in order to use the NanoCommons MIE tool with the default parameters, only a gene list is required as an input parameter.

Web interface

The web interface can be found at the following link: <https://armadillo.shinyapps.io/mies/> (see Figure 3). The user needs to input a list of genes/proteins and press the “Run query” button. The tool will calculate a prioritized list of MIEs with identified biological processes. A user can work with the result table in the web interface (filter functions were implemented) or download the table in a tab separated format.

The genes can be derived from *omics* experimental data, such as RNA-seq, microarrays, mass-spectrometry datasets, etc. By default, the tool performs incremental enrichment analysis. This list of genes is interpreted as an ordered list where elements are in the order of decreasing importance. This order of genes can represent some biological effects, for instance, fold changes of differential expression genes (DEGs), absolute expression values, etc. The web interface accepts a list of genes

(one gene per line) in different formats: gene symbols, gene IDs, microarray IDs, transcripts, uniprot protein ID, etc. Mixed types also can be entered.

For demonstration purposes, we placed two sample lists of differentially expressed genes derived from nanotoxicology microarray datasets. To input this list, click on the “example 1” or “example 2” hyperlinks located below the data entry field. The most relevant resulting gene sets and pathways for example 1 can be seen in Figure 4.

MIE prediction

Threshold: 0.05

Enter your list of genes (one gene per line):

Il6
Cxcl5
Saa1
Ml2
Gm1960
Cxcl1
Timp1
Pbp2
Aldh1a3
Hoxn

[example 1] [example 2]

Run query

MIE prediction tool performs functional enrichment analysis using custom gene sets.

Show 10 entries Search:

Event	term_id	name	p_value	genes	
1	MIE2	KEGG:04142	Lysosome	0.00584125972250547	Lilaf, Cd63, Hexa, Ctsc, Cltb, Ctsw, Ppt1, Manba, Gnptab, Slc11a1, Abca2, Ppt2, Gaa, Ap4e1, Ap3m2, Aga, Nagpa, Gga2, Atp6v0a1, Arsb, Ctsf
2	MIE3	GO:0006801	superoxide metabolic process	0.000222152617578984	Cxcl1, Noxo1, Sod2, Agt, Fbln5, Gch1, Tnf, Duox1
3	MIE3	GO:0090322	regulation of superoxide metabolic process	0.00299823855002102	Cxcl1, Agt, Fbln5, Gch1, Tnf
4	MIE3	GO:0006979	response to oxidative stress	0.00623995061061375	Il6, Zc3h12a, Sod2, Ptgs1, Dusp1, Slc7a11, Arg1, Fbln5, Areg, Sphk1, Lcn2, Plk3, Gch1, Tnf, Il18rap, Duox1, Epor, Fos, Arntl, Pdgfra, Hif1a, Bmp4, Fkbp1b, Akrl1b3, Il18bp, Pla2r1, Mpv17, Axl, Tat, Ccl19, Ercc6, Glrx, Mmp2, Pxdn, Mmp14, Txnrd1, Plekha1, Rgs14, Plk2b, Btk, Jak2, Mcl1, Chuk

Figure 4. MIE prediction tool - web interface.

As per all tools and services from NanoCommons, a key feature of the overall offer regarding the MIE tool is the accompanying training materials, which are currently being prepared for inclusion in the Library of training materials linked to the tools and services.

An **online training session** will be organized jointly with the NanoSafety Cluster WG A on Communication, Training and Education in order to promote the event to a wider community. The session will start with a brief introduction to the topics of AOPs and MIEs to the registered attendees. Thereafter, the workshop participants will be guided interactively through the web interface illustrated by one example each for the three different MIEs in place. The webinar recordings will be available online on the NanoCommons **infrastructure library** [<https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/library/>], the NanoCommons **YouTube channel** [<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCuawpRvXNpglwyltefTctw/videos>], and furthermore, promoted beyond the nanosafety community *via* the **ELIXIR TeSS** (https://tess.elixir-europe.org/content_providers/nanocommons#events).

Programming access

In order to increase the flexibility of the tool and how users can access it and/or integrate it into advanced computational workflows, we implemented programming access using R and Python languages.

R code

R library is a means to provide universal access to the MIE prediction tool and can be implemented into various automated pipelines. The `gost` function from `gprofiler2` library will calculate a prioritized list of MIEs with identified biological processes. The database (`gmt` file) is located on the `gprofiler` server and a token to access to the file and calculate statistics.

To utilise the R code version of the MIE prediction tool and the gene set database locally, the user needs only R (+ R studio, etc.) and should run the code as follows:

```
#####
```

```
#gprofiler2 can be installed from CRAN:
```

```
install.packages("gprofiler2")
```

```
#or via conda from the conda-forge channel:
```

```
conda install -c conda-forge r-gprofiler2
```

```
#running the code:
```

```
library(gprofiler2)
```

```
gost(query, organism = 'gp__2ruD_Ave9_Hk4', domain_scope = "known", correction_method =  
"gSCS", user_threshold = p_value, evcodes = TRUE, ordered_query = TRUE)$result
```

```
#####
```

Arguments:

`query` - list of differentially expressed genes/proteins. Different types of identifiers can be used: gene symbols, Entrez Gene IDs, transcripts, microarray IDs, uniprot protein ID, etc.

`p_value` - user-defined p-value threshold provides a possibility to additionally filter results. The threshold defaults to $p=0.05$, meaning that all significant results are shown. If the threshold is set to less than 0.05, matches with p-values above threshold are not shown.

`organism = 'gp__2ruD_Ave9_Hk4'` - predefined token for MIE gene set database.

`Correction_method` - the tool uses `g:SCS` multiple testing correction algorithm by default. Alternatively, False Discovery Rate (FDR), Bonferroni correction (BC) and Benjamini-Hochberg FDR (False Discovery Rate) can be used.

Python code

```
#Installing gprofiler
```

```
pip install gprofiler-official
```

```
#Initialization of the GProfiler object
```

```
from gprofiler import GProfiler
```

```
gp = GProfiler(
```

```
    user_agent='ExampleTool', #optional user agent
```

```
    return_dataframe=True, #return pandas dataframe or plain python structures
```

```
)
```

```
# Run MIE calculation
```

```
from gprofiler import GProfiler
```

```
gp = GProfiler(return_dataframe=True)
```

```
gp.profile(organism='gp__2ruD_Ave9_Hk4', query=DEGlist)
```

Conclusions

We have described a database and accompanying tooling that has been developed for the NanoCommons infrastructure for modelling the likelihood of MIE activation in the context of NM-driven toxicity and exemplified its functionalities with three MIEs related to inhalation toxicity. The tool can fill the gap in understanding of bionano interactions and facilitate reconstruction of the sequential chain of KEs in a particular AOP.

In this first version of the tool, we integrated gene expression predictors for three key types of MIEs: disruption of lung surfactant functionality, lysosomal destabilization, and oxidation of cell membrane. These MIEs were highlighted and described as the initial starting point of toxicological response to NMs for pulmonary AOPs in the SmartNanoTox project.

To create the MIE gene set database, we used published data from in vivo and in vitro experimental studies of nanoparticles toxicity and different signaling and functional databases. The software implementation of the tool enables the nanotoxicology community to easily access the results using a developed web interface or integrate the developed R/Python modules to various automated pipelines, including the Jaqpot computational platform and NanoCommons KB.

The tool will be extended and updated during the course of the NanoCommons project to address the needs of the nanosafety community, with this deliverable representing the first such tool to be integrated into the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase.

Identification of MIEs and their associated gene sets thus gives the first insight into the possible pathways altered by interaction with a NM. Then, to distinguish between the pathways automatically we need to create a library of biomarkers/genes for the remaining KEs of the specific pathways. This is still for future work.

Abbreviations

AO: Adverse outcome

AOP: Adverse outcome pathway

DEG: Differential expressed genes

GMT: Gene matrix transposed (file format)

GO: Gene ontology database

KE: Key Event

KEGG: Kyoto encyclopedia of genes and genomes

MIE: Molecular initiating events

NM: Nanomaterial

TA: Transnational Access

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Appendix: Model code for the MIE-GS model

```
library(shiny)

# Define UI for slider demo app ----
ui <- fluidPage(

  # App title ----
  titlePanel("Sliders"),

  # Sidebar layout with input and output definitions ----
  sidebarLayout(

    # Sidebar to demonstrate various slider options ----
    sidebarPanel(

      # Input: Simple integer interval ----
      sliderInput("integer", "Integer:",
        min = 0, max = 1000,
        value = 500),

      # Input: Decimal interval with step value ----
      sliderInput("decimal", "Decimal:",
        min = 0, max = 1,
        value = 0.5, step = 0.1),

      # Input: Specification of range within an interval ----
      sliderInput("range", "Range:",
        min = 1, max = 1000,
        value = c(200,500)),

      # Input: Custom currency format for with basic animation ----
      sliderInput("format", "Custom Format:",
        min = 0, max = 10000,
        value = 0, step = 2500,
        pre = "$", sep = ",",
        animate = TRUE),

      # Input: Animation with custom interval (in ms) ----
      # to control speed, plus looping
      sliderInput("animation", "Looping Animation:",
        min = 1, max = 2000,
        value = 1, step = 10,
        animate =
          animationOptions(interval = 300, loop = TRUE))

    ),

    # Main panel for displaying outputs ----
```

```
mainPanel(  
  
  # Output: Table summarizing the values entered ----  
  tableOutput("values")  
  
)  
)  
)  
  
# Define server logic for slider examples ----  
server <- function(input, output) {  
  
  # Reactive expression to create data frame of all input values ----  
  sliderValues <- reactive({  
  
    data.frame(  
      Name = c("Integer",  
              "Decimal",  
              "Range",  
              "Custom Format",  
              "Animation"),  
      Value = as.character(c(input$integer,  
                             input$decimal,  
                             paste(input$range, collapse = " "),  
                             input$format,  
                             input$animation)),  
      stringsAsFactors = FALSE)  
  
    })  
  
  # Show the values in an HTML table ----  
  output$values <- renderTable({  
    sliderValues()  
  })  
  
}  
  
# Create Shiny app ----  
shinyApp(ui, server)  
  
library(shiny)  
library(DT)  
# Define UI for slider demo app ----  
ui <- fluidPage(  
  
  # App title ----  
  titlePanel("MIE prediction"),  
  
  # Sidebar layout with input and output definitions ----
```

```

sidebarLayout(

# Sidebar to demonstrate various slider options ----
sidebarPanel(

  textInput("p_value", "Threshold:", 0.05),
  textAreaInput("list", "Enter your list of genes (one gene per line):", height = "200px"),
  #div(actionLink("example_data", "[example data]"),
  actionLink("example_data", "[example 1]"),
  actionLink("example_data2", "[example 2]"),
  HTML("</br>"),
  HTML("</br>"),
  actionButton("goButton", "Run query", #icon = icon("refresh"),
    style="color: #fff; background-color: #337ab7; border-color: #2e6da4"),
  HTML("</br>"),
  HTML("</br> MIE prediction tool performs functional enrichment analysis using custom gene
sets:"),
  HTML("</br> MIE1. Disruption of lung surfactant functionality"),
  HTML("</br> MIE2. Lysosomal destabilization"),
  HTML("</br> MIE3. Oxidation of cell membrane")
),

# Main panel for displaying outputs ----
mainPanel(

# Output: Table summarizing the values entered ----
#tableOutput("values")
DT::dataTableOutput("values"),
uiOutput("downloadData")

)
)
)

# Define server logic for slider examples ----
library(gprofiler2)
library(DT)

server <- function(input, output, session) {

#### > Example data ####
observeEvent(input$example_data, {
  updateTextAreaInput(session, "list", value = paste(readLines("data/DEGlistsimple.txt"), collapse =
"\n"))
}, ignoreInit = T)

observeEvent(input$example_data2, {

```

```

updateTextAreaInput(session, "list", value = paste(readLines("data/DEGlistsimple2.txt"), collapse =
"\n" )
}, ignoreInit = T)

# Reactive expression to create data frame of all input values ----
sliderValues <- eventReactive(input$goButton,{
  if(is.null(input$list)){
    return()
  }
  DEGlist = input$list
  DEGlist <- strsplit(DEGlist, "\n")
  #pws = as.data.frame(gost(DEGlist, organism = custom_id, domain_scope = c("known"),
correction_method = "gSCS",
  # user_threshold = input$p_value, evcodes = TRUE, ordered_query = TRUE)$result)
  pws = as.data.frame(gost(DEGlist, organism = 'gp__2ruD_Ave9_Hk4', domain_scope = c("known"),
correction_method = "gSCS",
    user_threshold = input$p_value, evcodes = TRUE, ordered_query = TRUE)$result)

  pws$intersection <- gsub(","," ",pws$intersection)
  pws <- as.data.frame(pws[,c(10,9,11,3,16)])
  colnames(pws) <- c("Event","term_id","name","p_value","genes")
  pws <- pws[order(pws$Event),]
  pws
})

# Show the values in an HTML table ----
# output$values <- renderTable({
# sliderValues()
# })
output$values = DT::renderDataTable({
  sliderValues()

})

output$downloadData <- renderUI({
  req(sliderValues())
  downloadButton("downloadData01")
})

output$downloadData01 <- downloadHandler(
  filename = "Results.txt",
  content = function(file) {
    write.table(sliderValues(), file, sep = "\t", row.names = F, quote = F)
  }
)
}

```